

Assumptions, agency, and authority: Mathematical modelling and students' socio-critical reasoning

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Data from the pandemic has afforded the use of real-world modelling problems in mathematics classes to consider socio-critical mathematics. From an ongoing project, we examine grade 9 students' written work while solving a modelling task to consider their agency and authority as mathematicians. We use this analysis to posit that the "making assumptions" stage of the modelling cycle is a key moment in modelling for students' agentic decision-making via making and revising assumptions as they construct a model. We discuss our emerging conception of students' modelling authority and agency and conjecture about the ways that teachers' instruction may afford or constrain these acts. We contribute to the emerging research on modelling instruction and students' socio-critical reasoning.

Mathematical modelling from a socio-critical perspective focuses on how mathematics can be used to critique and inform decision making within society (Barbosa, 2006). Mathematical modelling is a non-neutral process in this perspective; the interpretations of a problem context and the assumptions that follow shape the development of the model and resultant solution (Anhalt et al., 2018).

The practices involved in socio-critical modelling activities ask students to reason throughout real-world tasks such that they author mathematical and situational-relevant knowledge to read and critique their world. They also propose solution paths and logically connect their interpretations and decisions with their model and solution (Blum & Leiß, 2005). The modelling cycle stages of identifying the problem and making assumptions can be seen as critical for achieving these goals, as they offer explicit opportunities for students to act agentially (Anhalt et al., 2018). While goals for student engagement in complex, critical modelling tasks have recently gained traction in the literature (Kaiser, 2017), understanding how they might be actualized in instruction needs further study. Additionally, there is minimal literature on instructional strategies to support students' agency in complex modelling tasks (Elliott et al., 2019; Kaiser, 2017). In this paper, we explore how U.S. grade nine students engaged in a modelling task, which explicitly attended to making and reflecting on assumptions, and developed agency and authority via socio-critical reasoning.

Please cite as: Brunner, M., Elliott, R., & Stoddard, E. (2021). Assumptions, agency, and authority: Mathematical modelling and students' socio-critical reasoning. In D. Kollosche (Ed.), *Exploring new ways to connect: Proceedings of the Eleventh International Mathematics Education and Society Conference* (Vol. 1, pp. 137–140). Tredition. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5387558>

Theoretical background

Socio-critical mathematical modelling is an opportunity for productive disciplinary engagement that examines the relationships between *problematizing* and *resources*, and *authority* and *accountability*, while recognizing how power shapes contexts for learning (Agarwal & Sengupta-Irving, 2019; Engle, 2012). Specifically, students' identities and histories shape their modelling experiences, in part through the assumptions they make and the reasoning they provide. Socio-critical modelling tasks provide opportunities for students to consider contexts in which they problematize situations, assert their authority, and leverage resources to solve the problem. These tasks, which are often ill structured and complex, require students to identify conditions and assumptions central to the task (Blum & Leiß, 2005). In this study, we consider the resources students accessed to support their problematizing and resultant reasoning. Resources for modelling include those students access from previous modelling experiences as well as new resources they seek as they consider the problem. We also consider the balance between *authority* and *accountability* as students develop socio-critical modelling practices while engaged in a task. *Agency* can be seen when students are authorized to take a stance on a task or method, and this can develop into *authority* as mathematicians and thinkers as they get recognized for their ideas in a more public space. With authority comes the need for *accountability*, or the ability to articulate how and why one's ideas make sense. As students build authorship, they must also build accountability to disciplinary practices, mathematical logic, and to their community of learners and stakeholders. Through a socio-critical modelling task which leveraged student assumptions, we seek to explore the relationship between agency, authority, and accountability evident in students' reasoning.

Study context and methodology

Data for this paper draw from broader study of teachers' instructional tools for modelling. The students in this study had abruptly shifted to remote learning in March 2020. In this transition, their teacher posed the following scenario, *Toilet Paper (TP) Task* (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Modelling task for grade 9 students.

The grade 9 teacher and students had solved modelling tasks prior to remote learning using *modelling instructional routines*. These routines scaffolded students' learning of specific modelling practices, such as making assumptions and iteratively justifying models (Elliott et al., 2019). For the *TP Task*, the teacher asked students "to be thinking about those [modelling practices] ... as they went through the task and answering like what assumptions they made and how did that affect the final solution." Students were asked to independently complete

the task as directed in Figure 1. The student work and the teacher's reflection on the use of the task were data for this paper.

We examined students' work for their agentic moves to author their own interpretations of the task, their assumptions about the scenario, and the solution paths they developed. We also looked for ways students held themselves accountable to different sources of authority in their socio-critical reasoning processes. After reading the student work independently, the research team met to discuss themes of *agency/authority* and *accountability* in student work. We coordinated these data with the teacher's reflections provided during an interview on modelling instruction. Looking at the themes and evidence across all of the data allowed us to notice patterns in the ways students acted agentially to construct solutions to a societal problem and supported their reasoning.

Findings and discussion

As students presented their models they attended to conditions and assumptions that would shape their models. Students' agentic moves were made apparent when they considered conditions such as students' own household size and the potential length of the pandemic. They used these conditions to make assumptions about variables and quantities needed for their models, including the average rate of TP use when quarantined at home, average household size, gendered composition of family, and length of the pandemic. Students' histories and identities shaped the nature of conditions and assumptions they considered. Several students weighed the benefits and limitations of using single- versus double-ply toilet paper; one student noted that they "refused to even think about 1-ply toilet paper" and supported their reasoning by citing average American incomes to justify that a typical budget would be able to sustain 2-ply paper. These assumptions capture students' underlying attention to socioeconomics and humor, while grounding their arguments using data.

Students' attention to sources of accountability to justify features of models varied. A quarter of the students provided websites or organizational references and most students drew upon their own authority and solved the task taking into account their own household data. Given our analysis occurred 12 months into the pandemic, we found students' attention to accountability and authority to assert the duration of the pandemic most interesting. One student held themselves accountable to the World Health Organization and the Center for Disease Control to articulate their model. Another referenced that fact that "vaccines are still being tested and thus the pandemic will likely be in effect 900 days." A third stated that "scientists" have suggested the pandemic will last 52 weeks. Others relied on their own authority to determine the duration of the pandemic, making explicit that they were assuming the particular time frame; some students claimed it could last anywhere from 25 days to seven months.

We found a majority of students made explicit their assumptions which, given the teacher's initial prompt, may seem unremarkable. However, modelling instructional research and the teacher's prior instructional experience would suggest that students' find these practices challenging (Anhalt et al., 2018; Blum & Leiß, 2005). The teacher shared that the students are "getting used to not being able to get all the same answers in the end ... when they can figure out different ways they want to approach it and get into the problem, they

see it more as an exciting challenge.” The TP task afforded the students to leverage their experiences relevant to constructing a model, thus asserting their agency while also considering different sources of accountability to productively engage. Given the unprecedented nature of the pandemic, students’ attention to varying sources of accountability offers insights on how they were learning to read and write their world with mathematics through a lens of their experience and identity (Agarwal & Sengupta-Irving, 2019).

Conclusion

This ongoing study explores the possibilities for supporting students’ development of agency, authority, and accountability through socio-critical modelling tasks that require attention to assumptions. Utilizing the structure for reflecting on assumptions provided via a routine for modelling and the problematization of a relevant, open-ended task, we analyzed student work for evidence of their agency, authority, and accountability. These reflections show a willingness to construct arguments based on student-made assumptions and interpretations of the scenario. Further, students referenced outside authority as well as their own experiences to defend their mathematical ideas, developing reasoning strategies in line with disciplinary expectations of the logical process of decision-making in modelling activities.

Acknowledgements

The findings for this report are supported by CPM Education, grant number 20-0302. Any opinions, findings and conclusions expressed here are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the views of CPM Education.

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